
TCCC-ASM IN THE RUSSO–UKRAINIAN WAR: FIRST COMBAT EXPERIENCE AS A FACTOR IN THE GAP BETWEEN TRAINING AND PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS AMONG MOBILIZED MILITARY PERSONNEL

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tactical Combat Casualty Care for All Service Members (TCCC-ASM) aims to prepare military personnel to provide self-aid and buddy aid in combat. However, the extent to which acquired competencies are retained and translated into effective action during real combat remains poorly understood. This study evaluated the influence of first combat experience on the practical application of TCCC-ASM among mobilized military personnel during the Russo–Ukrainian War.

Methods: A multicohort observational study with a mixed retrospective–prospective design was conducted between August 2022 and May 2026. Data from five independent cohorts were integrated, including educational assessments, structured surveys, operational observations, prehospital medical documentation, medical evacuation records, and rehabilitation data. The primary endpoint was the actual implementation of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills during first combat experience. Transfer of training into operational practice was quantified using the authors’ Training-to-Performance Index (TP-index).

Results: A total of 1,961 participants were included. Although all participants successfully completed TCCC-ASM training, only 539 of 1,082 service members with combat experience (49.8%) subsequently encountered situations requiring the practical application of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills. Among 327 wounded personnel, self-aid was performed by 71 individuals (21.7%), whereas 78.3% required buddy aid. The TP-index for self-aid was 0.132 (95% confidence interval [CI], 0.104–0.163), indicating a substantial gap between successful training completion and performance under real combat conditions. Major barriers included severe pain, inability to recall procedures, panic reactions, limited visibility, and delayed evacuation. First combat experience was also associated with reassessment of the practical relevance of training and a unanimous demand for refresher training.

Conclusions: A measurable gap exists between successful completion of TCCC-ASM training and the practical implementation of acquired competencies during combat. This phenomenon, defined as the *Training-to-Performance Gap*, highlights the limitations of relying solely on educational outcomes when evaluating military medical training. The proposed TP-index provides a quantitative framework for assessing the transfer of training into operational performance and supports the implementation of structured refresher training following first combat experience.

Keywords TCCC-ASM; Tactical Combat Casualty Care; combat experience; military medicine; mobilized personnel; tactical medicine; combat casualty care; Russo-Ukrainian War

1 Introduction

“Everything in war is simple, but the simplest thing is difficult” - Carl von Clausewitz

Over the past two decades, Tactical Combat Casualty Care (TCCC) has become the internationally recognized standard for training military personnel in tactical medicine [1]. The implementation of TCCC principles is currently associated not only with a reduction in potentially preventable combat trauma mortality but also with a decreased risk of severe complications and disability resulting from combat injuries, including limb loss, vision loss, and other functionally significant consequences [2–5].

A special place within the TCCC system is occupied by the All Service Members (TCCC-ASM) level, which is intended to train all military personnel regardless of their military occupational specialty, rank, or prior medical education [6, 7]. The primary objective of TCCC-ASM is to establish a basic level of knowledge and skills required for self-aid and buddy-aid in combat trauma before the arrival of medical personnel or casualty evacuation [8].

The prolonged full-scale high-intensity Russian–Ukrainian war has become the largest armed conflict in Europe since the Second World War [9, 10] and has resulted in the unprecedented mobilization of a large number of Ukrainian service members who, prior to military service, possessed neither combat experience nor any military competencies, as many had not even completed compulsory military service and consequently found themselves rapidly, without any adaptation, in the most technologically saturated and extreme combat environment of the modern era [11]. For the majority of them, the TCCC-ASM course became the first and often the only structured training in tactical medicine before deployment to the combat zone.

Existing studies evaluating the effectiveness of such training predominantly assess it through knowledge examination results, performance in simulation-based scenarios conducted at training centers, or casualty survival indicators derived from hospital reporting systems [12]. Considerably less attention, however, has been devoted to understanding how military personnel apply the acquired knowledge and skills after entering the real hyper-transparent combat environment [13].

A distinctive feature of the Russian–Ukrainian war is the extensive use by the adversary of artillery, strike unmanned aerial systems, and loitering munitions [14], as well as stand-off weapons employing cluster munitions and remote detonation systems, the widespread use of chemical warfare agents, and thermobaric munitions against the background of continuous integrated aerial, ground, surface, and underwater sensor surveillance, thereby creating not only a 10–30 km kill zone but also a kill chain extending throughout the entire operational depth of the battlespace [15]. Consequently, the proportion of gunshot wounds has markedly decreased, shifting injury patterns toward explosive polytrauma with polystructural injuries, in which a single casualty may simultaneously sustain various combinations of traumatic brain injury (TBI), spinal cord injury (SCI), acoustic blast injury, injuries to body cavities and internal organs, burns, massive soft-tissue defects and destruction, bone injuries, and other forms of severe trauma [16, 17]. At the same time, a substantial proportion of tactical medical interventions is performed under the threat of repeated enemy strikes, under conditions of both degraded visibility and complete absence of illumination, markedly delayed evacuation (ranging from several hours to several days), severe resource shortages, and limited availability of medical personnel at the point of injury (POI) [18].

Collectively, these factors not only create an environment fundamentally different from that for which most TCCC-ASM training scenarios are designed but also call into question the direct transferability of training outcomes to real combat conditions, thereby allowing the hypothesis that a gap exists between the level of competence achieved during training and the ability of a mobilized service member to implement the acquired knowledge and skills during the first experience of combat.

Military psychology has consistently demonstrated that under conditions of intense stress and immediate threat to life, the effectiveness of decision-making and the performance of complex tasks may decline substantially [19]. The most characteristic manifestations of such responses include cognitive overload, stress-induced performance degradation, attentional narrowing, and tunnel vision [20]. Under these circumstances, individuals tend to rely on the most highly automated and well-rehearsed behavioral algorithms, whereas the execution of more complex cognitive and motor tasks may deteriorate [21]. Studies have also demonstrated that the magnitude of these responses largely depends on previous exposure to life-threatening situations, the level of training, and the availability of social support [22]. In particular, the presence of a calm and experienced leader or fellow service member may mitigate the adverse effects of stress on behavior and decision-making, as described by the concepts of social buffering and leadership-mediated stress reduction [23].

Despite the potential importance of understanding this phenomenon for improving TCCC-ASM training programs, the influence of the first combat experience on the practical application of acquired knowledge and skills among mobilized military personnel remains insufficiently investigated. Specifically, there is a lack of evidence regarding whether the first combat experience creates a gap between the level of competence achieved during training and the actual ability of military personnel to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in the combat environment.

An equally important issue concerns the long-term retention of TCCC-ASM training outcomes. At present, insufficient evidence exists regarding how well military personnel retain the acquired knowledge and skills several months after completing training, as well as how this process is influenced by the first combat experience, subsequent participation in combat operations, and previous military experience. Of particular interest is the comparison between mobilized service members and volunteer contract personnel, who may differ in terms of motivation, prior training, and adaptation to the combat environment.

Particular attention should also be given to the hypothesis that the first combat experience may represent a critical stage of reassessment and reinterpretation of previously acquired knowledge, whereby repeated training conducted after the first combat experience may prove more effective than additional training delivered before participation in actual combat operations.

Study Objective

The objective of this study was to evaluate the role of the first combat experience in the practical application of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills by mobilized military personnel during the Russian–Ukrainian war, to determine its significance in the formation of a gap between the level of training and actual behavior in the combat environment, and to investigate the characteristics of long-term retention of training outcomes and responsiveness to repeated tactical medicine training.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Design

The study was conducted as a multicohort observational study with a mixed (retrospective–prospective) design, in accordance with the STROBE recommendations [24], during the period from August 2022 to May 2026.

The primary hypothesis of the study was the assumption that a gap exists between the level of competence achieved during training under the TCCC-ASM program and the actual ability of military personnel to implement the acquired knowledge and skills during their first combat experience.

The study combined the analysis of training outcomes obtained at different stages of military personnel training and combat service with structured interviews of wounded combat participants regarding the characteristics of the practical application of tactical medicine knowledge and skills under real combat conditions.

2.2 Definition of the First Combat Experience

In the present study, the first combat experience was defined as the first episode of a mobilized service member’s direct exposure to a real life-threatening combat environment associated with the enemy’s use of firepower (artillery, mortar fire, strike unmanned aerial systems, FPV drones, small arms, or other means of attack), which required the individual to perceive, assess, and respond to the combat situation in real time. The presence of a first combat experience was determined regardless of whether the individual sustained an injury, personally employed a weapon, returned fire, or had direct visual contact with the enemy.

This operational definition is based on the widely accepted concept of combat exposure in military psychology, which considers combat exposure as a service member’s direct contact with a real combat threat, and is applied in the present study to identify the first such episode [25, 26].

2.3 Definition of the First Combat Event

The first combat event was defined as the specific episode of initial contact with the combat environment during which a service member acquired the first combat experience.

2.4 Data Sources

To achieve the objective of the study, five independent data sources were used, on the basis of which five cohorts (C1–C5) were established, representing different stages of training, acquisition of combat experience, combat service, and the medical pathway of mobilized military personnel (Table 1). The combined dataset provided the opportunity to perform both comparative and integrated analyses of the investigated phenomena.

Table 1: Data Sources and Characteristics of the Study Cohorts

Data Source / Cohort	Stage of Data Collection	Data Included in the Analysis
Data Source 1 (C1)	Basic training prior to first combat experience	Results of pre-course and post-course testing of mobilized service members during basic military training in training centers where instructor teams of the CIMMIC School of Tactical Medicine, CIMMIC Non-Governmental Organization, provided TCCC-ASM training before deployment to combat areas.
Data Source 2 (C2)	Refresher training after acquisition of combat experience within military units	Results of pre-course and post-course testing of service members after acquisition of their first combat experience during TCCC-ASM refresher courses conducted directly within military units performing missions in combat zones (training sessions were conducted in small groups of 10–15 personnel while observing all safety measures).
Data Source 3 (C3)	Refresher training after withdrawal of units from combat areas	Results of pre-course and post-course assessment and testing of service members during TCCC-ASM refresher courses conducted after withdrawal of military units from combat areas for restoration of combat capability and replenishment of personnel.
Data Source 4 (C4)	Survey of wounded personnel during tactical medical evacuation	Data from prehospital medical documentation, including Form 100 or its updated versions, Form No. 001/o “Primary Medical Card” and Form No. 002/o “Casualty Card,” in accordance with Order No. 879 of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine dated December 31, 2024 (an analogue of the TCCC Card), as well as structured interviews of wounded service members when permitted by the tactical situation and the casualty’s clinical condition.
Data Source 5 (C5)	Survey of wounded personnel during treatment and rehabilitation	Data from the certificate describing the circumstances of injury, wound, concussion, or mutilation (Appendix 5 to the Regulations on Military Medical Examination in the Armed Forces of Ukraine, approved by Order No. 402 of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine dated August 14, 2008, as amended), as well as structured interviews of service members undergoing neurosurgical treatment and neurorehabilitation at the Scientific-Practical Center of Neurorehabilitation “Nodus”.

Specific research objectives corresponding to the primary and secondary study endpoints were addressed by additionally combining the established cohorts into three analytical subgroups.

The **TO** (Training Outcomes; C1–C3) subgroup was designed to evaluate the educational outcomes of TCCC-ASM training, including changes in the level of theoretical knowledge and practical skills before and after training, their long-term retention, as well as the influence of acquired combat experience on the outcomes of repeated training.

The **FCE** (First Combat Experience; C2–C5) subgroup, which included military personnel who had acquired their first combat experience, served as the basis for investigating the transfer of TCCC-ASM training outcomes to the operational environment (transfer of training to the operational environment), the characteristics of the first combat event, combat stress factors, behavioral responses during the initial exposure to a real combat threat, and the influence of the first combat experience on the subsequent perception of training.

A separate **PUIC** (Performance Under Injury Conditions; C4–C5) subgroup, comprising wounded military personnel, was established to evaluate the actual application of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills following injury, the characteristics of self-aid and buddy-aid, and the factors influencing the performance of these interventions in the real combat environment.

2.5 Study Endpoints

The primary endpoint of the study was the frequency of the actual implementation of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills during the acquisition of the first combat experience. Skill implementation was defined as the performance by a service member of TCCC-ASM interventions in situations where their application was objectively necessary, tactically appropriate, and practically feasible.

The secondary endpoints of the study were:

1. Changes in the level of theoretical knowledge and practical skills following completion of the TCCC-ASM training program.
2. The level of knowledge and skill retention after acquisition of the first combat experience.
3. Self-assessed preparedness of military personnel to apply TCCC-ASM algorithms in the combat environment.
4. The frequency of the use of individual self-aid and buddy-aid interventions following combat injury.
5. Subjective assessment of the influence of the first combat experience on the perception of tactical medicine training.
6. Military personnel's attitudes toward the necessity of repeated (refresher) tactical medicine training after participation in combat operations.

2.6 Inclusion Criteria

Participants were included in the study if they met all of the following criteria:

- mobilized service members of the Armed Forces of Ukraine or other components of the Defense Forces of Ukraine;
- completion of a TCCC-ASM course at military training centers or military units with the participation of instructor teams from the CIMMIC School of Tactical Medicine;
- availability of documented pre-course and post-course assessment results (including practical skills evaluation) and testing;
- for specific study groups: presence or absence of the first combat experience following completion of TCCC-ASM training;
- voluntary informed consent to participate in the survey;
- for the wounded subgroup, an additional inclusion criterion was the presence of a combat injury sustained after completion of TCCC-ASM training.

2.7 Exclusion Criteria

The following participants were excluded from the study:

- individuals who had previous combat experience before completing their initial TCCC-ASM course;
- military personnel who had completed Combat Lifesaver (CLS) or Combat Medic/Corpsman (CMC) training before the initial survey;
- individuals with incomplete testing data;
- individuals who were unable to provide informed responses because of severe cognitive impairment, impaired consciousness, or a severe general medical condition;
- duplicate records of the same participant.

2.8 Potential Confounders

Given the multicohort observational design of the study, factors capable of influencing the practical application of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills independently of the acquisition of the first combat experience were taken into account during the analysis. The potential confounders included the service member's age, previous military experience (including prior compulsory military service), the interval between completion of TCCC-ASM training and acquisition of the first combat experience, the intensity of the first combat engagement, the number of subsequent combat missions, the presence of an experienced service member during the first combat experience, the occurrence of a combat injury, and the military occupational specialty or functional role of the service member.

2.9 Study Instruments

To collect field data, the authors developed a structured questionnaire (Supplementary Material 1: TCCC-ASM in the Russo-Ukrainian War: First Combat Experience as a Factor of the Gap Between Training and Practical Application of Knowledge and Skills Among Mobilized Military Personnel), designed in accordance with the TCCC-ASM doctrine and contemporary approaches to the assessment of educational and behavioral outcomes of military training. During its development, the principles of the Kirkpatrick Model for evaluating the transition from learning to behavior, the CROSS reporting standards for survey design and reporting, as well as the COSMIN methodology and Messick's validity framework were incorporated to ensure the content and construct validity of the instrument.

The conceptual framework of the questionnaire was based on the central hypothesis of the present study, according to which the first combat experience may represent a critical stage in the transition from the acquisition of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills to their practical implementation in the real combat environment. Accordingly, the subject of the study was not limited to the level of military training itself but primarily focused on the process through which training outcomes are transformed into actual behavior during combat events.

The primary study domain (Training-to-Performance Domain) was the implementation of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills following acquisition of the first combat experience. Within this domain, the sequential pathway of "training → emergence of need → opportunity for performance → actual implementation of the intervention" was evaluated, thereby enabling investigation of the potential gap between the level of competence achieved during training and the actual behavior of military personnel under combat conditions.

The secondary domains included participants' demographic characteristics, characteristics of the first combat experience, the first episode of practical TCCC-ASM application, reasons for failure to implement individual skills, self-aid and buddy-aid, performance under conditions of limited visibility, delayed evacuation and resource constraints, behavioral consequences of combat stress, retention of training outcomes, and the influence of the first combat experience on subsequent learning and responsiveness to refresher training. In addition, qualitative analysis of participants' open-ended responses was performed.

To analyze the reasons for failure to implement TCCC-ASM skills, a predefined list of potential barriers was developed before data collection based on the TCCC doctrine, the authors' clinical experience, analysis of combat casualty evacuations, and published evidence regarding the effects of combat stress on task performance.

The content validity of the questionnaire was ensured by aligning its structure with the educational objectives of the TCCC-ASM course, TCCC algorithms, and clinically relevant combat trauma scenarios that were regularly encountered during combat medical evacuations. Individual question blocks were specifically designed to assess not only the level of knowledge but also the conditions required for its practical implementation, potential barriers to its application, and the influence of the combat environment on military personnel's behavior.

To enhance the reliability of the collected information, survey findings were interpreted in conjunction with training assessment results, primary prehospital medical documentation, documentation describing the circumstances of combat injury, and medical evacuation records, thereby allowing reciprocal verification of individual reported events (data triangulation).

Before initiation of the main data collection, the questionnaire underwent repeated refinement and revision through practical field application during surveys of military personnel and medical evacuations conducted by the volunteer CIMMIC unit of the CIMMIC Non-Governmental Organization.

Thus, the structure of the questionnaire made it possible to evaluate not only the presence of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills but also the factors influencing their implementation, transformation, or deterioration following the first combat experience. The complete questionnaire structure is provided in Supplementary Material 1.

In addition to the structured questionnaire, the study used the results of the standard TCCC-ASM course assessment instruments provided within the Joint Trauma System (JTS) curriculum [27]. For the assessment of military personnel training at the TCCC-ASM level (both initial and refresher training), the results of pre-course and post-course testing, together with standardized practical skills assessments, were used. These assessments included evaluation of the participant's ability to perform Rapid Casualty Assessment, Tourniquet Application, Hemostatic Dressing/Wound Packing, Pressure Dressing, and Airway Maneuvers in accordance with the TCCC-ASM Skill Assessment Checklists.

Participation in the study was voluntary. All data were analyzed in a de-identified format. In accordance with the requirements of Operational Security (OPSEC) [28], the study was conducted without collecting or analyzing information capable of identifying specific military units, operational areas, evacuation routes, or any other information that could be of operational significance.

Statistical analyses were performed using MATLAB R2025a (MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA) with the application of both standard statistical procedures and author-developed data-processing scripts.

Considering the characteristics of conducting research under martial law and the requirements of OPSEC, the statistical analysis was based on aggregated results of standardized testing, structured questionnaires, and analysis of primary medical documentation. The analyses were performed predominantly at the level of aggregated measures describing the frequency and structure of the investigated phenomena.

The results are presented as absolute numbers, percentages (%), and corresponding 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) [29]. Categorical variables were analyzed using Pearson's χ^2 test or Fisher's exact test, depending on the expected cell frequencies [30].

The quantitative agreement between training outcomes and the actual application of Tactical Combat Casualty Care – All Service Members (TCCC-ASM) knowledge and skills was assessed using the integral Training-to-Performance Index (TP-index), developed by the authors specifically for the present study. The TP-index was defined as the proportion of situations requiring TCCC-ASM intervention in which a TCCC-ASM intervention was actually performed.

$$TP_{\text{index}} = \frac{N_{\text{TCCC-ASM interventions}}}{N_{\text{situations requiring TCCC-ASM}}} = \frac{N_{\text{self-aid}} + N_{\text{buddy-aid}}}{N_{\text{situations requiring TCCC-ASM}}} \quad (1)$$

where $N_{\text{TCCC-ASM interventions}}$ denotes the total number of TCCC-ASM interventions actually performed (self-aid plus buddy aid), and $N_{\text{situations requiring TCCC-ASM}}$ denotes the total number of situations in which a TCCC-ASM intervention was required.

TP-index values approaching 1.0 were interpreted as indicating a high level of agreement between the level of training and the actual behavior of military personnel in the combat environment.

The results are presented as absolute values, percentages, and corresponding confidence intervals. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

A complete list of abbreviations used throughout the manuscript is provided in Supplementary Table 1 (List of Abbreviations Used in the Manuscript).

3 Results

3.1 General Characteristics of the Study Population and Established Cohorts

During the study period, a total of 4,362 mobilized military personnel completed the TCCC-ASM training program.

After applying the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, as well as verifying the completeness and suitability of the available data, 1,961 participants (45.0% of the initial study population) were included in the final analysis and allocated to the following cohorts: C1—879 service members (44.8%), C2—415 (21.2%), C3—340 (17.3%), C4—173 (8.8%), and C5—154 (7.9%).

Within the predefined analytical subgroups, the TO (C1–C3) subgroup comprised 1,634 (83.3%) service members, the FCE (C2–C5) subgroup comprised 1,082 (55.2%), and the PUIC (C4–C5) subgroup comprised 327 (16.7%).

A small proportion of participants could be represented in more than one cohort as a result of subsequent military service, participation in combat operations, or sustaining a combat injury. However, the proportion of such cases was less than 1% and did not affect the results of the analysis.

3.2 Characteristics of the TO Subgroup

Training Outcomes All participants included in the analysis met the criteria for successful completion of the TCCC-ASM course. During the final assessment, 100% of service members achieved the passing threshold for theoretical training ($\geq 80\%$ correct answers) and successfully passed the practical examination.

The most common difficulties encountered during the practical assessment involved maintaining the correct sequence of casualty assessment and timely progression through the individual steps of the MARCH algorithm. In addition, according to instructors' observations documented during 139 training sessions, one of the most frequent challenges at the initial stage of training was memorizing the MARCH acronym and the order of its components. In response, many trainees spontaneously developed their own associative constructs and mnemonic strategies to facilitate recall of the algorithm.

At the same time, no errors involving critical life-saving interventions that could have resulted in failure of the practical examination were recorded upon completion of the training.

In groups where interim assessments demonstrated an increased frequency of errors or difficulties in mastering specific components of the algorithm, the actual duration of training was extended by an average of 1–2 hours until the predefined competency criteria had been achieved.

The baseline assessment of mobilized military personnel conducted between 2024 and 2026 demonstrated a low level of initial knowledge regarding the fundamental principles of TCCC-ASM and the algorithms for combat casualty care, despite the prolonged conduct of hostilities on the territory of Ukraine and the extensive coverage of tactical medicine in mass media and social media.

3.3 Characteristics of the FCE and PUIC Subgroups

Interval Between TCCC-ASM Training and the First Combat Experience Among 684 service members (63.2%), the first combat experience was acquired 1–3 months after completion of the TCCC-ASM training program, whereas in 398 (36.8%) this interval exceeded 3 months. Thus, for the majority of mobilized personnel, at least one month elapsed between completion of training and the first combat exposure.

Characteristics of the First Combat Experience The first combat experience was most frequently associated with FPV drone attacks, accounting for 410 cases (37.9%), followed by artillery shelling in 347 cases (32.1%) and mortar fire in 209 cases (19.3%). Attacks by strike unmanned aerial systems accounted for 12 cases (1.1%), combat involving small arms for 8 cases (0.7%), combined fire for 2 cases (0.2%), and other forms of long-range combat effects (guided aerial bombs, ballistic missiles, etc.) for 94 cases (8.7%). The resulting distribution differed substantially from the traditional perception of the first combat contact as direct engagement with the enemy at small-arms range.

Duration of the First Combat Contact Among 573 service members (53.0%), the duration of the first combat contact was less than 10 minutes; among 418 (38.6%), it ranged from 10 to 60 minutes; among 64 (5.9%), from 1 to 6 hours; and among 27 (2.5%), it exceeded 6 hours.

These findings indicate that, in the majority of cases, the first combat contact represented a short-duration combat episode.

Experienced Supervision During the First Combat Event Only 109 respondents (10.1%) reported the presence of an experienced service member with previous combat experience during their first combat event, indicating a limited role of direct mentorship during the initial adaptation to the combat environment.

Combat Activity Following acquisition of their first combat experience, the majority of mobilized service members ($n = 1025$, 94.7%) continued to participate in combat missions. Fifty-seven individuals (5.2%) sustained combat injuries during their first combat event and were evacuated for medical treatment and rehabilitation. Among the remaining participants, 56 (5.2%) subsequently completed 2–5 combat missions, 781 (72.2%) completed 6–10 missions, and 188 (17.4%) participated in more than 10 combat missions.

These findings indicate that the majority of respondents evaluated their first combat experience not as an isolated event but rather in the context of their subsequent cumulative combat activity.

Interval Between the First Combat Event and the Survey An interval of 1–3 months between the first combat event and the survey was recorded for 325 participants (30.0%), 3–6 months for 610 (56.4%), and more than 6 months for 147 (13.6%).

Thus, the majority of responses concerning the first combat experience represented a retrospective assessment of the experienced situation after a certain period of combat adaptation.

Transfer of TCCC-ASM Skills from Training to the Combat Environment A total of 692 participants (63.9%) reported witnessing the death or injury of military personnel and being placed in situations in which the application of TCCC-ASM principles was potentially appropriate.

However, the direct need to personally apply TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills occurred less frequently. During the first combat event, 217 service members (20.1%) reported such a need, whereas an additional 322 participants (29.8%) encountered this need only during subsequent combat missions. Among 543 service members (50.2%), no situations requiring the personal application of TCCC-ASM skills had occurred by the time of the survey.

Overall, 539 of the 1,082 service members (49.8%) encountered situations in which the practical application of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills was required. These situations included the respondents' own combat injuries (327 cases) and the provision of care to wounded fellow service members who were not included in the study cohort (212 cases), during which respondents were direct witnesses of the corresponding TCCC-ASM interventions but did not personally participate in providing medical care.

Among the 327 wounded participants (C4+C5), 71 service members (21.71%) were able to perform TCCC-ASM self-aid independently. This represented 6.6% of all respondents with combat experience and 13.2% of all situations in which the corresponding skills were required. In the remaining 256 cases (78.29%), the necessary interventions were performed by other personnel through buddy-aid.

All mobilized service members were equipped with individual first aid kits (IFAKs) and the required medical equipment, making deficiencies in material resources an unlikely explanation for the observed gap between the need for and the actual application of TCCC-ASM skills.

Factors Preventing Self-Aid Following Combat Injury Among wounded participants (C4+C5, $n = 256$; 78.29%) who were unable to provide TCCC-ASM self-aid, the principal barriers were:

- severe pain — 82 (32.03%);
- inability to recall the required procedure — 56 (21.88%);
- confusion and panic caused by the injury itself — 54 (21.09%);
- expectation that a medic would provide assistance — 49 (19.14%);
- intense enemy fire — 41 (16.02%);
- darkness — 38 (14.84%);
- impaired consciousness or disorientation — 12 (4.68%);
- limited access to the individual first aid kit due to its non-standard relocation — 10 (3.9%).

The results are presented for all factors with a frequency of at least 10 cases within the study group.

Provision of Care Under Conditions of Limited Visibility Although darkness as a barrier to self-aid following combat injury was reported in 38 cases (11.6%), difficulties in applying TCCC-ASM under conditions of limited visibility were reported by 352 participants in the FCE subgroup (32.5%).

These difficulties most commonly involved identification of bleeding sources and small thoracic and abdominal wounds, orientation within the contents of the individual first aid kit (IFAK), tourniquet application, hemorrhage control, assessment of the casualty's condition, and completion of primary medical documentation.

Furthermore, 114 participants (10.5%) reported that providing care in darkness itself resulted in errors, including twisted tourniquet straps on the lower extremities, additional injuries caused while cutting clothing, occlusive dressings applied to intact skin, unrecognized burns, and persistent uncontrolled hemorrhage. These errors were subsequently identified and corrected either by more experienced personnel (e.g., those trained to the Combat Lifesaver (CLS) level), by combat medics, or only during the evacuation phase.

These findings indicate that limited visibility may represent an additional influential factor that complicates the application of specific elements of TCCC-ASM in the contemporary combat environment.

Delayed Evacuation and Improvisation Within the PUIIC subgroup ($n = 327$), no cases of evacuation within less than 1 hour after injury were recorded. In 68 cases (20.8%), the time to evacuation was 1–6 hours; in 240 cases (73.4%), 6–24 hours; and in 19 cases (5.8%), 24–72 hours. No evacuations lasting more than 72 hours were documented in the study population.

The majority of wounded personnel remained at forward positions for prolonged periods, requiring service members trained at the TCCC-ASM level not only to perform the initial life-saving interventions but also to provide ongoing casualty care under resource-limited conditions, particularly in the absence of a combat medic or personnel trained to the TCCC-Combat Lifesaver (TCCC-CLS) level. Under these circumstances, the ability to improvise in practice became an important component of casualty survival and maintenance of physiological stability until evacuation.

Among the improvisation strategies described by the respondents, the most frequently reported were improvised methods for limb and torso immobilization using rubber tourniquets, additional warming measures, improvised stretchers and drag litters, identification of non-occlusive penetrating chest wounds by pouring water over the chest surface while

visually or acoustically detecting escaping air, independent withdrawal from dangerous areas under the protection of friendly unmanned systems and electronic warfare assets, and the use of adverse weather conditions as a means of reducing the risk of repeated enemy strikes during movement under radio silence.

Behavioral Consequences of the First Combat Stress Experience The behavioral consequences of combat stress were evaluated in subgroup C2–C5 ($n = 1082$) comprising mobilized service members who had acquired their first combat experience. The maximum severity score of 4 on the Numeric Rating Scale, adapted according to the concept of the Combat Exposure Scale within the structured questionnaire, was recorded for stressors including fear of repeated attack, sensory overload caused by battlefield noise, time pressure, and situational chaos.

Among the behavioral consequences, the highest scores were observed for the inability to recall TCCC-ASM procedures, psychological avoidance of tasks perceived as complex, and the ability to perform only the simplest actions. Among the procedures most frequently identified by respondents ($n = 59$, 5.45%) as provoking psychological resistance under real combat conditions was wound packing in a living casualty who was screaming in pain. At the same time, all respondents consistently emphasized that they had experienced no difficulty performing wound packing on training manikins during the course.

Impaired decision-making and exclusive attentional focus on the immediate threat were also highly pronounced.

These findings indicate that the first combat experience was accompanied by marked behavioral narrowing, whereby the execution of complex sequential algorithms could be replaced by the performance of only the simplest automated actions.

Retention of TCCC-ASM Training Outcomes Within the first month after training, 911 service members (84.2%) reported a decline in confidence in their ability to apply TCCC-ASM skills. After 1–3 months, 793 participants (73.3%) considered their level of training insufficient for independent execution of the algorithm under real combat conditions. After more than 3 months, 564 service members (52.1%) reported that they were no longer able to reproduce either the sequence of actions or individual components of the TCCC-ASM algorithm in the event of injury.

None of the participants in the subgroup confirmed complete preparedness to provide prehospital care according to TCCC-ASM standards at the time of acquiring their first combat experience.

The most rapid deterioration was observed in the recall of components requiring sequential execution of the algorithm or greater medical specificity, particularly the application of occlusive dressings, pressure dressings, and individual components of the MARCH algorithm. In contrast, the best retention was observed for simpler practical interventions, which respondents described as intuitively understandable or analogous to their previous civilian experience, including prevention of hypothermia, direct pressure on the wound, application of a compression bandage, and use of the contents of the pill pack.

These findings indicate a progressive decline in training outcomes following completion of the course.

Influence of the First Combat Experience on Subsequent TCCC Training Following acquisition of the first combat experience, all participants in the FCE subgroup ($n = 1082$) considered their previous TCCC-ASM training insufficient to ensure full preparedness for real combat conditions. At the same time, during refresher training the educational material was perceived as substantially easier to understand, while the results of the final assessment of theoretical knowledge and practical skills demonstrated a higher level of learning achievement compared with the initial training.

The topics that underwent the greatest reassessment following the first combat experience included control of massive hemorrhage, tourniquet application, self-aid, buddy-aid, the MARCH algorithm, casualty evacuation, management under conditions of delayed evacuation, and the influence of combat stress on decision-making. All respondents supported the necessity of mandatory refresher training as soon as possible after acquisition of the first combat experience.

The military personnel considered hemorrhage control, the use of universal medical interventions, actions under fire, and casualty evacuation to be the most valuable skills for practical application in the combat environment.

The most common recommendations for improving the training program included increasing the duration of the basic course, expanding the number of scenario-based training exercises conducted under both daytime and nighttime conditions, and mandatory implementation of refresher training after acquisition of the first combat experience.

Summarizing their experience, the respondents emphasized that under the conditions of modern warfare, knowledge and skills in tactical medicine are as essential for the survival of military personnel as training for the direct execution of combat missions.

Statistical Evaluation of Aggregated Measures and the TP-index Calculation of the 95% confidence intervals made it possible to assess the precision of the principal aggregated measures of the study (see *Supplementary Material 2: Statistical Analysis of the Training-to-Performance Gap Following First Combat Experience*). The proportion of service members who, during military service, encountered situations in which the application of TCCC-ASM principles was potentially appropriate was 63.9% (95% CI, 61.0–66.8%), whereas the actual need for personal application of the corresponding knowledge and skills occurred in 49.8% of cases (95% CI, 46.8–52.8%).

The integral measure of transfer of training outcomes to real-world practical performance, the *Training-to-Performance Index* (TP-index), was 0.132 (13.2%; 95% CI, 10.4–16.3%) for self-aid. Even when buddy-aid was taken into account, the overall training implementation index did not exceed 0.607 (60.7%; 95% CI, 56.4–64.8%). These values indicate the presence of a substantial gap between successful completion of the TCCC-ASM training program and the actual implementation of the corresponding skills in the combat environment.

Among wounded service members, the proportion of successful self-aid was 21.7% (95% CI, 17.4–26.6%), whereas in 78.3% of cases (95% CI, 73.4–82.6%) the required interventions were performed through buddy-aid. The most common barriers to independent performance of TCCC-ASM skills were severe pain (32.0%; 95% CI, 26.4–38.1%), inability to recall the required algorithm of actions (21.9%; 95% CI, 17.0–27.4%), confusion or panic reaction (21.1%; 95% CI, 16.3–26.6%), and expectation of assistance from a medic (19.1%; 95% CI, 14.5–24.5%).

Limited visibility was identified as an additional factor influencing the practical implementation of TCCC-ASM skills. Significant difficulties in performing individual elements of TCCC-ASM under conditions of limited visibility were reported by 32.5% of service members (95% CI, 29.7–35.4%), whereas 10.5% (95% CI, 8.8–12.5%) reported errors directly attributable to performing interventions in darkness.

Particularly pronounced were the indicators reflecting deterioration of training outcomes over time. Within the first month after completion of training, 84.2% of service members (95% CI, 81.9–86.3%) reported reduced confidence in their ability to apply TCCC-ASM skills. After 1–3 months, 73.3% (95% CI, 70.5–75.9%) considered their level of training insufficient for independent execution of the algorithm under combat conditions, while after more than 3 months, 52.1% (95% CI, 49.1–55.1%) were no longer able to reproduce the required sequence of actions. This temporal pattern indicates a progressive decline in training effectiveness following course completion and provides further justification for early refresher training after acquisition of the first combat experience.

Integration of these findings made it possible to develop an integral model describing the transition from training to the practical application of TCCC-ASM skills in the combat environment, visually illustrating the magnitude of the identified gap between training and actual service member behavior (*Training-to-Performance Gap*) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 illustrates the progressive reduction in the number of service members from the stage of successful completion of the TCCC-ASM training program to the actual application of the acquired skills in the real combat environment. The dashed line schematically denotes the *Training-to-Performance Gap*, representing the discrepancy between the level of competence achieved during training and the actual implementation of the corresponding skills under real combat conditions.

These findings indicate that successful completion of the TCCC-ASM course alone does not guarantee the subsequent independent performance of life-saving interventions following combat injury. They further underscore the necessity of considering the effects of combat stress, temporal deterioration of acquired skills, and the characteristics of the contemporary combat environment when planning the training of military personnel.

Taken together, the findings support the proposed hypothesis that a gap exists between the level of competence achieved during training under the TCCC-ASM program and the actual application of the corresponding competencies during combat operations. Within the framework of the present study, this phenomenon is defined as the *Training-to-Performance Gap*—a discrepancy between the competencies acquired during training and their practical implementation in the combat environment.

To provide an integrated synthesis of the study findings, a conceptual *Training-to-Performance Gap* model was developed, illustrating the sequential transition from successful completion of the TCCC-ASM training program to its practical implementation under real combat conditions. The model integrates training outcomes, the influence of factors associated with the first combat experience, the observed reduction in readiness for the independent application of skills following combat injury, and the potential role of refresher training as a mechanism for reducing the gap between training outcomes and the actual behavior of military personnel (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 illustrates the authors' conceptual model of the *Training-to-Performance Gap*, depicting the relationship between training outcomes achieved through the Tactical Combat Casualty Care–All Service Members (TCCC-ASM) program, the influence of first combat experience, the subsequent decline in knowledge retention, practical skills, and operational readiness, as well as the potential contribution of refresher training to reducing the identified gap between

Figure 1: Training-to-performance gap following TCCC-ASM training.

Refresher training may reduce the Training-to-Performance Gap and improve battlefield readiness.

Figure 2: Conceptual model of the Training-to-Performance Gap in TCCC-ASM: impact of first combat experience and the potential role of refresher training.

training outcomes and their practical implementation. The numerical values shown in the figure correspond to the aggregated findings of the present study.

The upper section summarizes the principal determinants contributing to the Training-to-Performance Gap, whereas the lower section presents the proposed conceptual framework for reducing this gap through the implementation of refresher training following first combat experience. The model is intended for illustrative purposes and reflects the practical implications derived from the findings of the present study.

Abbreviations used in Figure 2: Pre-course, assessment performed before participation in the TCCC-ASM course; Post-course, assessment performed after successful completion of the course; FCE, First Combat Experience; Injured personnel, indicators observed among wounded service members; Training-to-Performance Gap, the discrepancy between competencies achieved during training and their actual implementation in the combat environment; Refresher training, repeated training conducted after first combat experience.

4 Discussion

The principal finding of the present study was the identification of a persistent discrepancy between the outcomes of TCCC-ASM training and their practical implementation in the contemporary combat environment. Despite the successful completion of the training program by all study participants, the findings indicate that the knowledge and skills acquired during the course are not always translated into corresponding behavioral actions during the first combat experience. It is precisely to describe this phenomenon that the concept of the *Training-to-Performance Gap* is proposed in the present study.

The presented findings and the identified patterns suggest that the effectiveness of tactical medicine training cannot be fully evaluated solely on the basis of knowledge tests or standardized practical examinations. Such assessment tools characterize the level of learning achieved within a controlled environment; however, they do not fully reflect a service member's ability to implement the acquired competencies under conditions of a real combat threat. In this context, the findings support the need to distinguish between the concepts of *training outcomes* and *performance outcomes*.

The role of the first combat experience is of particular importance. The observed findings indicate that this stage may represent a critical transition point between the training environment and the operational combat environment. The first encounter with a real threat to life changes the context of decision-making, reshapes the perceived importance of individual components of training, and establishes new behavioral priorities. As a consequence, some competencies that were successfully demonstrated during training appear to be insufficiently integrated for effective application under real combat conditions.

Importantly, the identified gap cannot be explained solely by an insufficient level of initial training. On the contrary, all participants completed the course in accordance with the established competency requirements. This suggests that the combat environment itself plays a substantial role, combining physical exhaustion, uncertainty, the threat of repeated attack, time pressure, sensory overload, and the simultaneous need to perform multiple competing tasks. Under such conditions, even well-acquired algorithms may not be implemented in their entirety or may be replaced by simpler behavioral responses.

The practical significance of these findings lies in the possibility of considering the *Training-to-Performance Gap* as a distinct object for evaluating the effectiveness of military medical training. Within this framework, the principal outcome measure becomes not only successful course completion but also the service member's ability to implement the acquired competencies after entering the real combat environment.

One of the most important practical implications of the present study is the potential role of refresher training following acquisition of the first combat experience. The present observations suggest that only after encountering the realities of combat do military personnel develop a more practical understanding of the importance of individual TCCC-ASM components, thereby creating favorable conditions for deeper assimilation of the educational material during subsequent training. In this context, the first combat experience may be regarded not only as a risk factor for the development of the *Training-to-Performance Gap*, but also as a potential opportunity for its subsequent reduction.

Particular attention should be given to factors extending beyond traditional training scenarios that directly influence the transfer of acquired competencies into the combat environment. The present analysis demonstrates that the effective application of TCCC-ASM skills depends not only on the level of previous training but also on the conditions under which their implementation becomes necessary. Limited visibility, the absence of experienced mentorship, and the need for independent decision-making create additional cognitive and organizational demands that are rarely reproduced during conventional training. Under such circumstances, the critical determinant is no longer the mechanical execution of individual algorithms but rather the ability to adapt them to the specific tactical situation. Within this context, practical

improvisation may be regarded not as a deviation from training but as one of the manifestations of successful transfer of its fundamental principles into real combat operations. Even during the acquisition of the first combat experience, the implementation of complex multistep algorithms may become compromised, whereas simpler and more automated actions are preferentially adopted. This observation is consistent with contemporary concepts regarding the influence of combat stress on cognitive processes and warrants further investigation in specifically designed studies.

Taken together, the findings support the concept of the *Training-to-Performance Gap* as a distinct phenomenon of military medical training and indicate the need to move beyond the exclusive evaluation of training outcomes toward assessment of the actual transfer of acquired competencies into the combat environment.

5 Limitations

The interpretation of the present findings should take into account several limitations. First, the study was conducted during the active phase of the Russian–Ukrainian war, which limited the collection and use of individualized data because of Operational Security (OPSEC) requirements. Consequently, the analyses were performed predominantly at the level of aggregated measures, precluding detailed modeling of the influence of individual factors at the individual participant level.

Part of the findings was based on structured surveys conducted among service members after acquisition of combat experience or following combat injury. Therefore, the influence of individual perception, retrospective evaluation of events, and recall bias cannot be completely excluded. Nevertheless, the use of multiple independent data sources, including training assessment results, prehospital medical documentation, medical evacuation records, and structured surveys of military personnel, reduced the risk of systematic bias in the interpretation of the findings.

The study population was assembled during different periods of the war and included service members with varying levels of combat exposure, duration of military service, intensity of combat operations, and intervals between completion of training and acquisition of the first combat experience. Although this heterogeneity increases the practical relevance of the findings, it may also influence the comparability of individual subgroups.

The structured questionnaire developed by the authors was designed in accordance with the TCCC-ASM doctrine, the educational objectives of the course, and typical scenarios of contemporary combat trauma; however, it did not undergo an independent comprehensive psychometric validation. Therefore, the findings should primarily be interpreted as reflecting the real-world field experience of military personnel within the investigated study population.

Furthermore, the findings reflect the specific characteristics of the contemporary Russian–Ukrainian war and may not be fully generalizable to other theaters of military operations, military contingents, or tactical medicine training systems.

Despite these limitations, the large cohort of mobilized military personnel, the multicohort study design, and the integration of training outcomes with data derived from real combat experience provided a comprehensive understanding of the transfer of TCCC-ASM skills from the training environment to the practice of modern warfare.

6 Future Research

Further studies are required to investigate the factors influencing the implementation of TCCC-ASM skills in the real combat environment, particularly the roles of combat stress, limited visibility, delayed evacuation, and previous combat experience.

A promising direction for future research is the conduct of prospective multicenter studies using individualized participant-level data to further elucidate the mechanisms underlying the development of the *Training-to-Performance Gap* and to further validate the integral *Training-to-Performance Index* (TP-index).

Particular interest should also be directed toward determining the optimal timing of refresher training following acquisition of the first combat experience, as well as evaluating the effectiveness of training scenarios that most closely reproduce the conditions of contemporary warfare.

The concept of the *Training-to-Performance Gap* may potentially be applicable not only to TCCC-ASM training but also to other domains of military training in which outcomes are determined by the ability to translate acquired competencies into effective performance under real operational conditions.

7 Conclusions

1. A gap between the training outcomes achieved during the TCCC-ASM program and their practical implementation following acquisition of the first combat experience was identified among mobilized service members who successfully completed TCCC-ASM training. Within the framework of the present study, this phenomenon is defined as the *Training-to-Performance Gap*.
2. Nearly half of the service members encountered situations during military service that required the application of TCCC-ASM knowledge and skills; however, independent performance of life-saving interventions following combat injury was observed in only a small proportion of the wounded personnel.
3. The practical implementation of TCCC-ASM training in the combat environment was characterized by a low value of the *Training-to-Performance Index* (TP-index = 0.132) for self-aid, quantitatively reflecting the magnitude of the identified *Training-to-Performance Gap*.
4. The implementation of TCCC-ASM skills occurred under conditions that differed substantially from standard training scenarios and were characterized by the influence of remote means of attack, limited visibility, delayed evacuation, and limited opportunities for direct mentorship.
5. The first combat experience was accompanied by a reassessment of the practical importance of individual components of TCCC-ASM training and generated a demand for refresher training among the service members who participated in the study.
6. The present findings support the use of the *Training-to-Performance Gap* concept and the integral TP-index as tools for evaluating the effectiveness of tactical medicine training programs not only on the basis of training outcomes but also according to the extent to which the acquired competencies are transferred to the real combat environment.

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9 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The study was conducted independently. All materials used in this research were utilized exclusively for scientific purposes. The findings and conclusions presented herein reflect solely the views of the authors and do not represent the official position of any governmental, military, or non-governmental organization.

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11 Author Contributions

Oleksandr Kulyk: conceived and designed the study, developed the study methodology, performed data analysis and interpretation, drafted and revised the manuscript, prepared the figures and tables, and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Olena Maidannyk: participated in data collection, primary data processing, interpretation of educational and behavioural findings, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

12 Ethical Approval

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (2013 revision) and applicable national regulations governing biomedical research, personal data protection, and the handling of sensitive operational information in Ukraine.

The study was based exclusively on de-identified and aggregated observational data obtained during routine educational, medical, and medical-evacuation activities conducted by the CIMMIC Non-Governmental Organization in cooperation with the Armed Forces of Ukraine. No experimental interventions were performed, no identifiable personal data were collected, and all information was analyzed in a fully anonymized form.

To ensure operational security (OPSEC), no information capable of identifying military units, operational locations, evacuation routes, operational procedures, or individual participants was collected, stored, or analyzed.

The study involved a secondary analysis of observational data collected during participants' day-to-day activities and did not interfere with their medical care, education or operational activities.

13 Consent for publication

Not applicable.

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Supplementary Table 1. List of Abbreviations Used in the Manuscript

Abbreviation	Definition
ASM	All Service Members
CES	Combat Exposure Scale
CI	Confidence Interval
CIMMIC	Civilian Medical Military Cooperation
CLS	Combat Lifesaver
CMC	Combat Medic/Corpsman
COSMIN	Consensus-Based Standards for the Selection of Health Measurement Instruments
CROSS	Checklist for Reporting Results of Surveys
FCE	First Combat Experience
FPV	First-Person View
IFAK	Individual First Aid Kit
JTS	Joint Trauma System
MARCH	Massive Hemorrhage, Airway, Respiration, Circulation, Hypothermia/Head Injury
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NRS	Numeric Rating Scale
OPSEC	Operational Security
POI	Point of Injury
PUIC	Performance Under Injury Conditions
SCI	Spinal Cord Injury
STROBE	Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology
TBI	Traumatic Brain Injury
TCCC	Tactical Combat Casualty Care
TCCC-ASM	Tactical Combat Casualty Care – All Service Members
TO	Training Outcomes
TP-index	Training-to-Performance Index

Supplementary Material 1. Structured Questionnaire

TCCC-ASM in the Russo-Ukrainian War: First Combat Experience as a Factor of the Gap Between Training and Practical Application of Knowledge and Skills Among Mobilized Military Personnel

SECTION 1. DEMOGRAPHIC AND MILITARY SERVICE DATA

Participant Study Code

Age

Military Rank

Branch of Service

Date of Mobilization

Did you complete mandatory military service prior to mobilization?

- Yes
- No

Did you have any military experience prior to mobilization?

- Yes
- No

Did you have any combat experience before the full-scale Russo-Ukrainian War?

- Yes
- No

Date of Initial TCCC-ASM Training

Have you completed a refresher (re-training) course?

- Yes
- No

Date of Most Recent Refresher Training

SECTION 2. FIRST COMBAT EXPERIENCE

Operational Definition

First combat experience was defined as the first exposure of a service member to actual enemy lethal effects or direct combat threats, regardless of whether injury occurred.

Time Between TCCC-ASM Training and First Combat Experience

- Less than 1 week
- 1–4 weeks
- 1–3 months
- More than 3 months

Primary Type of First Combat Exposure

- Artillery strike
- Mortar attack
- FPV drone attack
- Strike UAV attack
- Small-arms engagement

- Combined engagement
- Other

Duration of First Combat Exposure

- Less than 10 minutes
- 10–60 minutes
- 1–6 hours
- More than 6 hours

Were casualties present during this event?

- Yes
- No

Did a situation requiring TCCC intervention occur during this event?

- Yes
- No

Was an experienced service member present nearby?

- Yes
- No

Number of Combat Missions Completed After First Combat Experience

- 1
- 2–5
- 6–10
- More than 10

Time Between First Combat Experience and Survey Administration

- Less than 1 month
- 1–3 months
- 3–6 months
- More than 6 months

Rate the Following Characteristics of Your First Combat Experience (0–10)

0 = minimal
10 = maximal

- Perceived threat to life
- Intensity of hostile fire
- Psychological stress
- Situational uncertainty

SECTION 3. FIRST REAL-WORLD TCCC APPLICATION

When did the first real need to apply TCCC skills occur?

- During the first combat experience
- During a later combat event
- Never occurred

The situation involved:

- My own injury
- Injury of a fellow service member
- Multiple casualties
- Casualty evacuation
- Other

SECTION 4. CORE STUDY DOMAIN

Translation of TCCC-ASM Training Into Real-World Performance

For each skill, indicate:

- A. This skill was included in my training
- B. A situation occurred in which this skill could have been required
- C. I had the physical ability to perform the action
- D. I had the tactical opportunity to perform the action
- E. The required equipment was available
- F. I performed the action independently
- G. The action was performed by another person

Skills

Skill	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Tourniquet application	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Self-aid	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Buddy aid	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Massive hemorrhage identification	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Pressure dressing application	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Individual first aid kit (IFAK) utilization	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Casualty evacuation preparation	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Actions under limited visibility conditions	<input type="checkbox"/>						

SECTION 5. REASONS FOR FAILURE TO IMPLEMENT A SKILL

If a skill was not performed, identify the primary reason:

- Intense hostile fire
- Threat of secondary attack
- Personal injury
- Severe pain
- Darkness
- Lack of time
- Lack of equipment
- Inability to access medical equipment
- Inability to recall the procedure
- Confusion/disorientation
- Waiting for assistance
- Other

SECTION 6. SELF-AID AND BUDDY AID

(For injured participants only)

What was your first action after injury?

- Self-aid
- Buddy aid
- Calling for assistance
- Waiting for assistance
- Cannot remember

Did you attempt self-aid?

- Yes
- No

Who provided the first actual medical intervention?

- Myself
- Fellow service member
- Combat medic
- Other

If self-aid was not attempted, why?

- Physically unable to act
- Unable to access IFAK
- Did not recognize injury severity
- Waiting for assistance
- Confusion/disorientation
- Other

SECTION 7. OPERATIONS UNDER LOW-LIGHT CONDITIONS

Were TCCC actions performed during darkness or severely limited visibility?

- Yes
- No

Was artificial illumination available?

- Yes
- No

Which tasks became more difficult?

- Identification of hemorrhage
- Identification of chest injuries
- Accessing IFAK contents
- Tourniquet application
- Casualty assessment
- Evacuation
- Other

Did limited visibility contribute to errors?

- Yes
- No

SECTION 8. DELAYED EVACUATION

Time to Evacuation

- Less than 1 hour
- 1–6 hours
- 6–24 hours
- 24–72 hours
- More than 72 hours

Were available medical resources sufficient?

- Yes
- No

Were improvised solutions required?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please describe:

SECTION 9. BEHAVIORAL EFFECTS OF COMBAT STRESS

Rate each item from 0 to 4

0 = Not present

4 = Extremely severe

Stressors

- Fear of secondary attack
- Noise overload
- Time pressure
- Situational chaos

Behavioral Consequences

- Unable to recall procedures
- Unable to make decisions
- Focused exclusively on the threat
- Able to perform only the simplest actions

Influence of an Experienced Service Member

0 = No effect

4 = Critical positive effect

SECTION 10. RETENTION OF TRAINING OUTCOMES

How long after training did you begin to lose confidence in your TCCC skills?

- Less than 1 month
- 1–3 months
- More than 3 months
- No loss of confidence

Which skills deteriorated most rapidly?

Which skills were retained best?

SECTION 11. EFFECT OF FIRST COMBAT EXPERIENCE ON SUBSEQUENT LEARNING

Before my first combat experience, I rated my readiness to apply TCCC as:

0–10

After my first combat experience, I rate my readiness to apply TCCC as:

0–10

Following my first combat experience, I consider my previous training to have been:

- Adequate
- Partially adequate
- Inadequate
- Unsure

During refresher training, the material was perceived as:

- Much easier to understand
- Somewhat easier to understand
- Unchanged
- More difficult to understand

Which topics became clearer after real combat exposure?

- Tourniquet application
- Self-aid

- Buddy aid
- Casualty evacuation
- Low-light operations
- Combat stress and psychological factors

Should refresher training be mandatory after first combat experience?

- Yes
 - No
-

SECTION 12. OPEN-ENDED QUESTIONS

1. Which elements of TCCC-ASM proved most useful in real combat conditions?

 2. What was missing from your training?

 3. What should be added to TCCC-ASM training?

 4. What should be changed in the preparation of mobilized military personnel?

 5. What was the most important lesson learned from your first combat experience?

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Methodological Note

Supplementary Material 2. Statistical Analysis of the Training-to-Performance Gap Following First Combat Experience.

Section	Parameter	Count	Total	Percent	C195_ Lower	C195_ Upper
Sample structure	Final analytical sample	1961	4362	44,96	43,47	46,45
Cohort distribution	C1	879	1961	44,82	42,61	47,06
Cohort distribution	C2	415	1961	21,16	19,37	23,04
Cohort distribution	C3	340	1961	17,34	15,69	19,09
Cohort distribution	C4	173	1961	8,82	7,60	10,17
Cohort distribution	C5	154	1961	7,85	6,70	9,13
Analytical subgroups	TO	1634	1961	83,32	81,60	84,95
Analytical subgroups	FCE	1082	1961	55,18	52,94	57,39
Analytical subgroups	PUIC	327	1961	16,68	15,05	18,40
Time to FCE	1–3 months	684	1082	63,22	60,26	66,10
Time to FCE	>3 months	398	1082	36,78	33,90	39,74
Type of FCE	FPV drones	410	1082	37,89	34,99	40,86
Type of FCE	Artillery	347	1082	32,07	29,29	34,94
Type of FCE	Mortar fire	209	1082	19,32	17,00	21,80
Type of FCE	Strike UAV	12	1082	1,11	0,57	1,93
Type of FCE	Small arms	8	1082	0,74	0,32	1,45
Type of FCE	Combined fire	2	1082	0,18	0,02	0,67
Type of FCE	Other remote effects	94	1082	8,69	7,08	10,53
FCE duration	<10 min	573	1082	52,96	49,93	55,97
FCE duration	10–60 min	418	1082	38,63	35,72	41,61
FCE duration	1–6 h	64	1082	5,91	4,58	7,49
FCE duration	>6 h	27	1082	2,50	1,65	3,61
Experienced support	Experienced servicemember nearby	109	1082	10,07	8,34	12,02
TCCC exposure	Potentially relevant TCCC situation	692	1082	63,96	61,01	66,82
TCCC need	Actual need for TCCC-ASM application	539	1082	49,82	46,79	52,84
TP-index	Self-help TP-index	71	539	13,17	10,43	16,32
TP-index	Self-help + buddy-aid TP-index	327	539	60,67	56,40	64,82
PUIC self-help	Self-help among wounded	71	327	21,71	17,37	26,58
PUIC self-help	No self-help among wounded	256	327	78,29	73,42	82,63
Barriers to self-help	Severe pain	82	256	32,03	26,36	38,13
Barriers to self-help	Recall failure	56	256	21,88	16,97	27,45
Barriers to self-help	Panic/disorientation	54	256	21,09	16,26	26,61
Barriers to self-help	Waiting for medic	49	256	19,14	14,51	24,50
Barriers to self-help	Enemy fire	41	256	16,02	11,74	21,09
Barriers to self-help	Darkness	38	256	14,84	10,72	19,80
Barriers to self-help	Confusion	12	256	4,69	2,45	8,04
Barriers to self-help	IFAK access	10	256	3,91	1,89	7,07
Limited visibility	Difficulties under limited visibility	352	1082	32,53	29,75	35,41
Limited visibility	Errors associated with darkness	114	1082	10,54	8,77	12,52
Evacuation delay	1–6 h	68	327	20,80	16,53	25,60
Evacuation delay	6–24 h	240	327	73,39	68,25	78,11
Evacuation delay	24–72 h	19	327	5,81	3,53	8,93
Skill retention	Confidence decrease within 1 month	911	1082	84,20	81,88	86,32
Skill retention	Low confidence within 1–3 months	793	1082	73,29	70,55	75,91
Skill retention	Unable to recall after >3 months	564	1082	52,13	49,10	55,14